

Oxidation of some vicinal and non-vicinal diols by morpholinium chlorochromate : A kinetic and mechanistic study

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Abstract : The kinetics of oxidation of four vicinal, four non-vicinal diols and two of their monoethers by morpholinium chlorochromate (MCC) have been studied in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO). The main product of oxidation is the corresponding hydroxycarbonyl compound. The reaction is first order in MCC and the diols. The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen ion dependence is taking the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+]$. The oxidation of [1,1,2,2-²H₄]-ethanediol exhibits a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 5.82$ at 298 K). The reaction has been studied in nineteen different organic solvents and the solvent effect has been analysed using Taft's and Swain's multiparametric equations. The temperature dependence of the kinetic isotope effect indicates the presence of a symmetrical transition state in the rate-determining step. A suitable mechanism has been proposed.

Keywords : Correlation analysis, diols, halochromates, kinetics, mechanism, oxidation.

Introduction

Halochromates have been used as mild and selective oxidizing reagents in synthetic organic chemistry¹⁻⁵. Morpholinium chlorochromate (MCC) is also one such compound used for the oxidation benzyl alcohols⁶. Most other halochromates are salts of heterocyclic bases with chlorochromic acid. We have been interested in the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of the oxidation by complexed Cr^{VI} species and have reported several mechanistic studies by halochromates⁷⁻¹⁰. There seems to be no report on the oxidation aspects of diols using morpholinium chlorochromate (MCC). Therefore, it was of interest to investigate the kinetics of the oxidation of some vicinal and non-vicinal diols by MCC in DMSO. A suitable mechanism has also been postulated.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry : The homogeneity of the DNP derivatives indicated the formation of only one product in each case. Under our reaction conditions, therefore, there is no observable oxidation of the second hydroxy group. This may be due to the presence of a large excess of the diol over MCC. The overall reaction may, therefore, be

written as eq. (1).

MCC undergoes a two-electron change. This is in accord with the earlier observations with both structurally similar pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC)⁷ and MCC¹⁰. It has already been proved earlier that both pyridinium fluorochromate (PFC)¹¹ and pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC)¹² act as two electron oxidants and are reduced to chromium(IV) species.

The rate laws and other experimental data were obtained for all the diols investigated. As the results were similar, only representative data are reproduced here. There is no noticeable oxidation of pinacol by MCC under our reaction conditions.

Rate laws : The reaction is found to be first order with respect to MCC. The individual kinetic runs were strictly first order to MCC. Further the pseudo-first order rate constants do not depend on the initial concentration of MCC. The rate increases linearly with an increase in the concentration of diol (Table 1). Thus the reaction is first order with respect to diol also. Fig. 1 depict a typical kinetic run.

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of ethanediol by MCC at 298 K

10^3 [MCC] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Diol] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^5 k_{obs}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.0	0.10	5.22
1.0	0.20	10.2
1.0	0.40	20.7
1.0	0.60	30.6
1.0	0.80	41.4
1.0	1.00	49.5
2.0	0.40	18.5
4.0	0.40	21.7
6.0	0.40	19.0
8.0	0.40	22.5
1.0	0.20	11.7 ^a

^aContained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

Fig. 1. Oxidation of ethanediol by MCC : A typical kinetic run.

Test for free radicals : The oxidation of diols, by MCC, in an atmosphere of nitrogen failed to induce the polymerisation of acrylonitrile. Further, addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the rate (Table 1). We further confirm the absence of free radicals in the reaction pathway, the reaction was carried out in the presence of 0.05 mol dm⁻³ of 2,6-di-*t*-butyl-4-methylphenol (butylated

hydroxytoluene or BHT). It was observed that BHT was recovered unchanged, almost quantitatively.

Effect of temperature : The rates of oxidation of all the diols were determined at four different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 3). The log k_2 at different temperature is linearly related to the inverse of the absolute temperature in all cases (Fig. 2). The Arrhenius equation is, therefore, valid for these oxidations.

Effect of hydrogen ions : The reaction is catalyzed by hydrogen ions (Table 2). The hydrogen-ion dependence has the following form : $k_{obs} = a + b [H^+]$. The values of a and b for ethanediol are $2.57 \pm 0.11 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$ and $4.86 \pm 0.17 \times 10^{-4} mol^{-1} dm^3 s^{-1}$ respectively ($r^2 = 0.9949$).

Table 2. Dependence of the reaction rate on hydrogen-ion concentration

[Ethanediol] 0.10 mol dm ⁻³ ; [MCC] 0.001 mol dm ⁻³ ; Temp. 298 K [TsOH] (mol dm ⁻³)	0.10	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80	1.00
$10^5 k_{obs}$ (s ⁻¹)	6.03	7.20	8.82	10.8	12.6	15.3

Fig. 2. Oxidation of diols by MCC : Effect of temperatures.

Table 3. Rate constants and the activation parameters for the oxidation of diols by MCC in DMSO

Diols	$10^4 k_2$ (s ⁻¹)				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288	298	308	318 K			
Ethane-1,2-diol	2.10	4.95	11.7	27.0	61.7 ± 0.9	-102 ± 3	91.8 ± 0.8
Propane-1,2-diol	9.63	21.6	46.8	108	58.5 ± 1.0	-100 ± 4	88.2 ± 0.9
Butane-2,3-diol	44.1	93.6	189	396	52.9 ± 0.7	-107 ± 2	84.6 ± 0.6
Butane-1,2-diol	13.5	29.7	61.2	135	55.5 ± 0.9	-107 ± 3	87.4 ± 0.7
Propane-1,3-diol	15.3	34.2	79.2	171	59.0 ± 0.7	-95 ± 2	87.0 ± 0.5
Butane-1,3-diol	19.8	41.4	87.3	180	53.5 ± 0.7	-111 ± 2	86.6 ± 0.5
Butane-1,4-diol	23.4	51.3	117	143	57.2 ± 0.6	-97 ± 2	86.0 ± 0.5
Pentane-1,5-diol	33.3	69.3	144	297	53.0 ± 0.7	-109 ± 2	85.3 ± 0.6
3-Methoxy-butan-1-ol	39.6	82.8	180	369	54.3 ± 0.7	-103 ± 2	84.8 ± 0.6
2-Methoxyethanol	7.02	16.2	41.4	88.2	61.1 ± 0.1	-90 ± 3	88.3 ± 0.8
DED ^a	0.34	0.85	2.07	4.95	65.4 ± 0.6	-104 ± 2	96.2 ± 0.5
k_H/k_D	6.18	5.82	5.65	5.45			

^a[1,1,2,2-²H₄]ethane-1,2-diol.

Kinetic isotope effect : To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step, the oxidation of DED was studied. The results recorded in Table 4, showed that the reaction exhibited a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 5.82$ at 298 K).

Effect of organic solvents : The oxidation of ethanediol was studied in 19 different organic solvents. The choice of solvents was limited due to the solubility of MCC and its reaction with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with the solvents chosen. The kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values of k_2 are recorded in Table 4.

Table 4. Effect of solvents on the oxidation of propane-1,2-diol by MCC at 298 K

Solvents	$10^5 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	Solvents	$10^5 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
Chloroform	51.3	Acetic acid	7.94
1,2-Dichloroethane	63.1	Cyclohexane	2.29
Dichloromethane	60.3	Toluene	18.2
DMSO	216	Acetophenone	95.5
Acetone	56.2	THF	33.9
<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylformamide	117	<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	24.5
Butanone	41.7	1,4-Dioxane	29.5
Nitrobenzene	77.6	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	15.1
Benzene	22.4	Carbon disulphide	9.77
Ethyl acetate	21.4		

The values of $\log k_2$ at 288 K and $\log k_2$ at 318 K for the oxidation of ten compounds are linearly related ($r^2 = 0.9848$) (Fig. 3). The value of isokinetic temperature evaluated^{13,14} from this plot is 874 ± 36 K. The correlation

Fig. 3. Exner's isokinetic relationship in the oxidation of diols by MCC.

was tested and found genuine by using Exner's criterion¹⁵. A linear isokinetic correlation implies that all the compounds are oxidized by the same mechanism. The linear correlation here involves two typical monohydric

alcohols viz. 2-methoxyethanol and 3-methoxybutan-1-ol. Thus it seems likely that the diols also behave like monohydric alcohols towards MCC. This is further supported by the isolation of hydroxyaldehyde as the product and the resistance of pinacol towards the oxidation by MCC.

Reactivity oxidizing species : The observed hydrogen dependence suggests that the reaction follows two mechanistic pathways, one is acid-independent and the other is acid-dependent. The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of MCC to yield a protonated Cr^{VI} species which is a stronger oxidant and electrophile (2).

Formation of a protonated Cr^{VI} species has earlier been postulated in the reactions of structurally similar quinolinium fluorochromate (QFC)¹⁶ and MCC¹⁷.

Solvent effect : The rate constants, k_2 , for the oxidation of ethanediol in 18 organic solvents (CS₂ was not considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) did not exhibit any significant correlation in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship (3) of Kamlet *et al.*¹⁸.

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + \alpha\alpha \quad (3)$$

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, β the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities and α is the hydrogen bond donor acidity. A_0 is the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 13 have a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of eq. (3), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β are given below eqs. (4)–(7).

$$\log k_2 = -4.44 + (1.60 \pm 0.21)\pi^* + (0.25 \pm 0.17)\beta - (0.25 \pm 0.16)\alpha \quad (4)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8560; \text{sd} = 0.19; n = 18; \Psi = 0.42$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.38 + (1.69 \pm 0.21)\pi^* + (0.17 \pm 0.17)\beta \quad (5)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8327; \text{sd} = 0.20; n = 18; \Psi = 0.43$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.41 + (1.73 \pm 0.20)\pi^* \quad (6)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8214; \text{sd} = 0.20; n = 18; \Psi = 0.43$$

$$\log k_2 = -2.64 + (0.47 \pm 0.37)\beta \quad (7)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0912; \text{sd} = 0.45; n = 18; \Psi = 0.98$$

Here n is the number of data points and Ψ is the Exner's statistical parameter¹⁹.

Kamlet's¹⁸ triparametric equation explains *ca.* 86% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's criterion¹⁹ the correlation is not even satisfactory (*cf.* eq. (4)). The major contribution is of solvent polarity. It alone accounted for *ca.* 82% of the data. Both β and α play relatively minor roles.

The data on the solvent effect were analysed in terms of Swain's²⁰ eq. (8) of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents also.

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (8)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. $(A + B)$ is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of eq. (8), separately with A and B and with $(A + B)$.

$$\log k_2 = (0.48 \pm 0.04)A + (1.77 \pm 0.03)B - 4.23 \quad (9)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9948; \text{sd} = 0.04; n = 19; \Psi = 0.08$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.22 (\pm 0.59)A - 2.55 \quad (10)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0086; \text{sd} = 0.47; n = 19; \Psi = 1.02$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.74 (\pm 0.09)B - 4.39 \quad (11)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9566; \text{sd} = 0.09; n = 19; \Psi = 0.21$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.34 \pm 0.17(A + B) - 4.27 \quad (12)$$

$$r^2 = 0.7905; \text{sd} = 0.22; n = 19; \Psi = 0.47$$

The rates of oxidation of ethanol in different solvents showed an excellent correlation in Swain's equation (*cf.* eq. (9)) with the cation-solvating power playing the major role. In fact, the cation-solvation alone account for *ca.* 99% of the data. The correlation with the anion-solvating power was very poor. The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$, also accounted for *ca.* 79% of the data. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 79% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.5465$; $\text{sd} = 0.32$; $\Psi = 0.69$).

Correlation analysis of reactivity : The rates of oxidation of the four vicinal diols in DMSO showed the excellent correlation with Taft's σ^* values²¹ with negative reaction constants (Table 5), this indicates the presence of

Table 5. Reaction constants of the oxidation of vicinal diols by MCC

T (K)	ρ^*	R^2	sd	ψ
288	-1.35 ± 0.12	0.9851	0.08	0.14
298	-1.30 ± 0.11	0.9856	0.08	0.13
308	-1.26 ± 0.09	0.9908	0.06	0.11
318	-1.19 ± 0.09	0.9893	0.06	0.12

an electron-deficient rate-determining step. The fact that σ^* values alone able to account for 99% of the data showed that steric factors do not play any significant role in the reaction. The magnitude of the reaction constants decreases with an increase in the temperature, this shows that selectivity decreases with an increase in the reactivity. Here $\Sigma \sigma^*$ represents the sum of the substituent constants for the substituents present on the two alcoholic carbons of the vicinal diols.

Mechanism :

The presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect confirms the cleavage of an α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step. The negative value of the polar reaction constant together with substantial deuterium isotope effect indicate that the transition state approaches a carbocation in character. Hence the transfer of hydride-ion from diol to the oxidant is suggested. The hydride-transfer mechanism is also supported by the major role of cation-solvating power of the solvents.

The hydride ion transfer may take place either by a cyclic process via an ester intermediate or by an acyclic one-step bimolecular process. This postulation is supported by an analysis of the temperature dependence of kinetic isotope effect. Kwart and Nickel²² have shown that a

study of the dependence of the kinetic isotope effect on temperature can be gainfully employed to resolve this problem. The data for protio- and deuterio-ethanols, fitted to the familiar expression $k_H/k_D = A_H/A_D \exp(E_a/RT)$ ^{23,24} show a direct correspondence with the properties of a symmetrical transition state in which the activation energy difference (ΔE_a) for k_H/k_D is equal to the zero-point energy difference for the respective C-H and C-D bonds (≈ 4.5 kJ/mol) and the frequency factors and the entropies of activation of the respective reactions are nearly equal. The similar phenomena have also observed earlier in the oxidation of hydroxy acids by QFC and benzyl alcohols by MCC. Bordwell²⁵ has documented a very cogent evidence against the occurrence of concerted one-step bimolecular processes by hydrogen transfer and it is evident that in the present studies also the hydrogen transfer does not occur by an acyclic bimolecular process. It is well established that intrinsically concerted sigmatropic reactions, characterized by transfer of hydrogen in a cyclic transition state, are the only truly symmetrical processes involving a linear hydrogen transfer²⁶. Littler²⁷ has also shown that a cyclic hydride transfer, in the oxidation of alcohols by Cr^{VI} , involves six electrons and, being a Hückel-type system, is an allowed process. Thus the overall mechanism is proposed to involve the formation of a chromate ester in a fast pre-equilibrium step and then a disproportionation of the ester in a subsequent slow step via a cyclic concerted symmetrical transition state leading to the product (Scheme 1). The observed hydrogen-ion dependence can be explained by assuming a rapid reversible protonation of the chromate ester (A) with the protonated ester decomposing at a rate faster than (A) (Scheme 2).

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

It is of interest to recall that pinacol is oxidized by chromic acid but not by MCC. Chatterjee and Mukherji²⁸ reported an abrupt change from butane-2,3-diol to pinacol, the latter reacting very fast. As pointed out by Littler²⁷, a cyclic ester mechanism is forbidden in the diol-Cr^{VI} reaction. Chromic acid oxidation of pinacol may therefore involve two one-electron steps. Chromic acid oxidations are known to induce polymerization of acrylamide under certain conditions²⁹. No such observation has yet been recorded with MCC. Thus the capability of chromic acid and the inability of MCC to act as a one-electron oxidant may explain the different behaviour of pinacol towards these two oxidants.

Experimental

Materials : The diols and the monoethers (BDH or Fluka) were distilled under reduced pressure before use. MCC was prepared by the reported method⁶. [1,1,2,2-²H₄]Ethane diol (DED) was prepared by reducing diethyl oxalate with lithium aluminium deuteride³⁰. Its isotopic purity, determined by its NMR spectrum, was 95 ± 3%. Due to the non-aqueous nature of the medium, toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. TsOH is a strong acid and in a polar solvent like DMSO, it is likely to be completely ionized. Solvents were purified by the usual methods³¹.

Product analysis : Product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. In a typical experiment, ethanediol (0.1 mol) and MCC (0.01 mol) were taken in

DMSO (100 ml) and the mixture was allowed to stand in the dark for *ca.* 10 h to ensure completion of the reaction. Most of the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and residue treated overnight with an excess (250 ml) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 2 mol dm⁻³ HCl. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, recrystallized from ethanol and weighed. The product was found identical (m.p. and mixed m.p.) with an authentic sample of DNP of hydroxyethanol. The oxidation state of chromium in completely reduced reaction mixtures, determined by an iodometric method, was 3.90 ± 0.15.

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were followed under pseudo-first order conditions keeping a large excess (× 15 or greater) of the diols over MCC. The temperature was kept constant to ±0.1 K. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of MCC spectrophotometrically at 370 nm for up to 80% of the reaction. No other reactant or product has any significant absorption at this wave-length. The pseudo-first order rate constants, *k*_{obs}, were evaluated from the linear (*r* = 0.995–0.999) plots of log [MCC] against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within ±4%. All experiments, other than those for studying the effect of hydrogen ions, were carried out in the absence of TsOH.

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